

Pattern of microbial flora and antibiotic sensitivity among healthy adults with bacteriuria in a university community in south-eastern Nigeria

VITALIS OBISIKE OFURU ^{1,*}, JENNIFER ONUZULIKE ² and OKIGBEYE DANAGOGO ¹

¹ Department of Surgery, Urology Division, University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

² Department of Health Services, Federal University of Technology, Owerri (FUTO), Imo State, Nigeria.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(03), 609–617

Publication history: Received on 03 February 2023; revised on 05 March 2023; accepted on 08 March 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.3.0378>

Abstract

Background: Knowledge of common urine microbial flora and the sensitivity pattern are essential in determination of empirical antibiotic usage

Aim: To determine the common microbiological flora in the urine of apparently healthy adults and the sensitivity and resistance pattern.

Materials and Methods: A cross sectional survey of the pattern of urinary microbial organisms and their sensitivity and resistance antibiotic pattern among adult population in a university community. Multi staged random sampling was used to obtain up to 465 respondents. Clean catch mid-stream urine samples were collected and prepared. Culture was done in three different media for identification and isolation of bacteria. The antimicrobial sensitivity was determined using sensitivity disk by Kirby-Bauer method. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 25 at 95% confidence interval and a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant. Data was presented in frequencies and percentages as appropriate.

Results: Female respondents (76.97%) were more. 20-24 age group had the highest number of respondents (50.66%). 36.29% had bacteria growth in their urine. *Escherichia coli* (63.6%) is the commonest microbial agent found in the urine of the population, followed by *staph aureus* (20%), then *Klebsiella* (16.4%). The isolated organisms were mostly resistant to the common antibiotics. However, *E. coli* was slightly susceptible to Levofloxacin (37.1%), Ciprofloxacin (31.4%) and Gentamycin (30%). *Klebsiella* showed mild susceptibility to Levofloxacin (15%), Ciprofloxacin (12%) and Ceftriazone (9%).

Conclusion: *E.coli*, *staph aureus* and *Klebsiella* are the dominant microbial flora found while levofloxacin, ciprofloxacin, ceftriazone and augmentin are the most sensitive antibiotics.

Keywords: Microbial flora; Asymptomatic; Bacteriuria; Sensitive antibiotics; Healthy adult population; FUTO

1. Introduction

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is a general term for infections involving any part of the urinary tract namely the kidneys, ureters, bladder and urethra. UTI is known to be among the most common bacterial infections acquired in the community and in hospitals¹ and account for a large number of hospital visits worldwide². In Nigeria, Jumbo and his colleagues³ documented 12.3% and 9.3% prevalence of community acquired and nosocomial UTIs respectively. The

* Corresponding author: VITALIS OBISIKE OFURU

prevalence of UTIs in Nigeria, according to Akinsete and Ezeaka⁴ also vary across geo-political zones with reported rates of 11.96% in South West-Nigeria, 2.7% in an urban setting in south east and 13.7% in Northern Nigeria.

Urinary tract infections are caused by both Gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria and these include: uropathogenic *E. coli*, *klebsiella pneumoniae*, *staphylococcus saprophyticus*, *enterococcus faecalis*, group *B streptococcus* (GBS), *proteus mirabilis*, *pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *staphylococcus aureus*; *Candida* spp. which are fungal organisms also cause urinary tract infection¹. Most of these pathogens are present naturally in the peri-urethral and perianal area, and ascend through the urethral orifice to cause UTI¹.

The diagnosis of urinary tract infection is based on symptoms and or results of investigations: symptoms depend on the part of the urinary tract involved, the causative organisms, the patient's ability to exert an immune response to it, the severity of the infection and age of the person; Symptomatic urinary tract infection can be acute or chronic, complicated or uncomplicated⁵. Symptoms may include fever, burning sensations while urinating, suprapubic pain and pyuria⁵.

Asymptomatic bacteriuria is the presence of bacteria in the urine of an individual that does not have symptoms and signs of urinary tract infection, provided that the urine was collected without contamination⁶⁻⁹. Patients with asymptomatic bacteriuria show no obvious symptoms and appear clinically normal. Several researches have been conducted on asymptomatic bacteriuria in varying age-groups and cohorts⁶⁻⁹. Delzell and Lefevre⁶ documented a global prevalence of 2 – 10%. In Nigeria, Olamijulo et al⁷ documented a higher prevalence rate of 14.6%. Prevalence of 20-35% has been documented among women attending antenatal care in Ghana⁸. In children, a meta-analysis on prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria conducted by shakkih and others⁹ showed a prevalence of 0.37% (95% CI 0.09 -6.82) in boys and 0.47% (95 CI 0.36 – 0.59) in girls. The sub group with the highest prevalence from their meta-analysis were uncircumcised males less than 1 year of age and females greater than 2 years of age. Other groups at high risk of asymptomatic bacteriuria include spinal cord injury patients on intermittent clean catheterization, patients with indwelling urethral catheter, diabetics, the elderly and institutionalized patients.

A common clinical dilemma is whether or not to treat patients with asymptomatic bacteriuria. Whereas clinical benefit has been demonstrated in treatment of pregnant women with asymptomatic bacteriuria¹⁰, it has not been so with the other cohorts. In fact, Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of asymptomatic bacteriuria in adults¹¹ advocates that screening for and treatment of asymptomatic bacteriuria should not be recommended for premenopausal non pregnant women, diabetic women, older persons living in the community, elderly institutionalized subjects, persons with spinal cord injury and catheterized patients while catheter remains in situ. This is because of increased incidence of adverse antimicrobial effects and possibility of reinfection with antibiotic resistant organisms.

Screening for asymptomatic bacteriuria should not be done if there is no intention to treat the subject but screening is indicated in two scenarios: where asymptomatic bacteriuria is associated with adverse outcomes and the intervention with antimicrobial treatment improves those outcomes and in a research study to further explore the biology or clinical significance of bacteriuria¹¹

In this study therefore, we intend to determine the common microbiological flora and the sensitivity pattern in the urine of apparently normal sexually active adults in a university community. This knowledge could be useful in the determination of antibiotics to use in empirical treatment of clinical cases of urinary tract infections.

2. Material and methods

This research utilized cross-sectional survey design. The study was carried out between January and February 2022 among university students of Federal University of Technology Owerri (FUTO). FUTO is the foremost university of technology established in the South East Nigeria in the year 1980. It is a tertiary institution situated in Owerri West Local Government Area of Imo State bounded by four communities namely Ihiagwa, Ezi-Obodo, Obinze and Umuagwo. There are twelve (12) faculties in it namely the School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology (SAAT), School of Basic Medical Sciences, School of Biological Sciences (SOBs), School of Engineering (SSET), School of Environmental Sciences (SOES), School of Health Technology (SOHT), School of Information and Communication Technology (SICT), School of Management Technology (SMAT), School of Physical Sciences (SOPS), School of Postgraduate Studies (SGPS) and Directorate of General Studies. Each of these facilities have a minimum of five Departments. Students study their respective courses in these departments. The students are over 22,000 in population. There are hostel accommodations within the campus for students which are provided by the university management but a reasonable number of students live off-campus within the neighboring communities. Sick students are treated in the university health centre which is located within the institution, whenever they fall ill.

The study was carried out at the Faculties and Departments of the institution. It utilized a self-administered questionnaire. The variables considered were age, sex, symptoms of urinary tract infection (for exclusion), antibiotic treatment (for exclusion), urinalysis, urine culture, sensitivity and resistance pattern.

The study population was limited to apparently normal individuals, who did not have any symptoms of urinary tract infection. This might be a source of bias.

The exclusion list included those who voluntarily opted out of the study, students who had taken antibiotics medication for any other disease condition in the past two weeks before sample collection and menstruating female students. Students who reported any symptom and signs of urinary tract infection were also excluded from the study. We issued sterile universal bottles to each student for collection of clean catch midstream urine specimens. They were educated on how to collect urine with as little contamination as possible. We thought female students to cleanse their vulva and around their urethral opening with clean water, and to part their vulva while passing urine in order to get clean catch urine. The containers were serially labelled and gender indicated. We did not write names to avoid bias and ensure confidentiality. The corresponding questionnaires from the respective students were also tagged with the same numbers labelled on their sterile bottles. We examined the collected clean catch mid-stream urine samples ~~were~~ macroscopically, microscopically, and chemically. We Cultured the urine in three different media for identification and isolation of bacteria. Materials used included Bunsen burner, wire loop, blood agar, chocolate agar, MacConkey agar, face mask, latex gloves. The universal bottle containing midstream urine was mixed by inverting the bottle. The lid was passed through the Bunsen flame three times to reduce the load of micro-organisms on it. The lid was opened and a loopful of urine was collected using the wire loop. The loopful was inoculated in the culture medium to make primary inoculum. The culture medium was then placed in the incubation chamber at 37°C for 24 to 48hours for the growth of micro-organism. Urine culture was considered to have significant bacteriuria when colony forming units $\geq 10^5$ / ml of voided urine was obtained. A single pure colony was suspended in nutrient 6 and sub cultured in machinery plate and blood agar plate incubated at 37°C for 24hour. Isolates were identified using colony morphology and biochemical test. The antimicrobial sensitivity was determined using sensitivity disk by Kirby-Bauer method.

The population of students in the institution was estimated to be 25,000.00. The formula for survey developed by Yaro Yamen was used to determine the minimum sample size as follows: $n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2}$ where n = minimum sample size, N = Estimated Total population of students, and e = desired precision/level of significance, usually 5% (0.05) at 95% Confidence Interval (CI). Hence, $n = 25,000 / 1+25,000 \times 0.05^2 = 400$.

Five hundred (500) students were selected for the study via random sampling technique. Multi staged sampling was done. In the first stage, the twelve faculties were sampled randomly and five of the faculties chosen. In the second stage, five departments were randomly selected from each of the faculties and in the final stage of sampling twenty (20) students from each department were selected giving a total of 100 students in each faculty. We had a meeting with the respective department heads and student representatives who made the students available on agreed dates. The final selection of the 20 students from each department was done through balloting. Each of the selected student was given a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was pretested prior to the study to ensure accuracy, appropriateness and to ascertain it was understandable. The collected data were checked for consistency and accuracy. The sterility of the prepared culture was checked by incubating 5% of the prepared culture randomly selected for 24hours at 37°C. Laboratory identification procedure such as inoculation of culture media, colony characterization and measuring of antibiotic susceptibility were checked. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 25. All analysis was done at 95% confidence interval and a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant. Data was presented in frequencies and percentages as appropriate. The association of bacteria and demographic characteristics was assessed using the chi-square statistic.

3. Results

Table 1 Demographic characteristics

	Frequency(n=456)	Percent(%)
Gender		
Male	105	23.03
Female	351	76.97
Age-Groups(years)		
15-19	57	12.50
20-24	231	50.66
25-29	126	27.63
30-34	33	7.24
35-39	9	1.97

The table shows that the number of female respondents (351, 76.97%) was more than the male respondents (105, 23.03%). Also, 20-24 age group had the highest number of respondents (50.66%)

Figure 1 Prevalence of Bacteria growth on culture

The figure shows that 165 (36.29%) respondents had bacteria growth in their urine while 291 (63.8%) had no bacteria growth.

Table 2 Association of Age groups and bacteriuria

Age-group(years)	Bacteriuria n(%)	No Bacteriuria n(%)	Total n, (%)	Chi-square(p-value)
15-19	33(57.89)	24(42.11)	57(100.0)	24.76 (0.015) *
20-24	60(25.97)	171(74.03)	231(100.0)	
25-29	63(50.00)	63(50.00)	126(100.0)	
30-34	6(18.18)	27(81.82)	33(100.0)	
35-39	3(33.33)	6(66.67)	9(100.0)	

Statistically significance (p<0.05)

The table showed that the proportion of bacteriuria was significantly higher ($p = 0.015$) among the age group of 25-29 in comparison to other age groups. Hence, the occurrence of bacteriuria was significantly associated with the age group 25-29 among the study population.

Table 3 Distribution of Bactria culture

Bacteria isolated	Frequency(n=165)	Percent (%)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	105	63.6
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	33	20.0
<i>klebsiella</i>	27	16.4

The table shows that *Escherichia coli* (63.6%) is the commonest microbial agent found in the urine of the population, followed by *Staph aureus* (20%), then *Klebsiella* (16.4%).

Table 4 Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of *Escherichia coli* Isolate

<i>Escherichia Coli</i>			
Antibiotics	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)	Total (%)
Augmentin	15(14.3)	90(85.7)	105(100.0)
Ceftriazone	21(20.0)	84(80.0)	105(100.0)
Ciprofloxacin	33(31.4)	72(68.6)	105(100.0)
Levofloxacin	39(37.1)	66(62.9)	105(100.0)
Amoxycilline	9(8.6)	96(91.4)	105(100.0)
Gentamycin	30(28.6)	75(71.4)	105(100.0)
Nalidixic Acid	3(2.9)	102(97.1)	105(100.0)
Streptomycin	3(2.9)	102(97.1)	105(100.0)
Ampicillin	3(2.9)	102(97.1)	105(100.0)

The table shows that the *E. coli* isolated was mostly resistant to most of the common antibiotics. However, it was slightly susceptible to Levofloxacin (37.1%), Ciprofloxacin (31.4%) and Gentamycin (30%).

Table 5 Antibiotic susceptibility of *Klebsiella* organism

<i>Klebsiella organism</i>			
Antibiotics	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)	Total (%)
Augmentin	2(22.2)	21(77.8)	27(100)
Ceftriazone	9(33.3)	18(66.7)	27(100.0)
Ciprofloxacin	12(44.4)	15(55.6)	27(100.0)
Levofloxacin	15(55.6)	12(44.4)	27(100.0)
Amoxycilline	6(22.2)	21(77.8)	27(100.0)
Gentamycin	6(22.2)	21(77.8)	27(100.0)
Nalidixic acid	0(0.00)	27(100.0)	27(100.0)
Streptomycin	0(0.00)	27(100.0)	27(100.0)
Ampicillin	3(11.1)	24(88.9)	27(100.0)

The table shows that the Klebsiella organism was mainly resistant to most of the common antibiotics but showed mild susceptibility to Levofloxacin (15%), Ciprofloxacin (12%) and Ceftriazone (9%).

Table 6 Antibiotic susceptibility of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Antibiotics	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>		
	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)	Total (%)
Augmentin	12(36.6)	21(63.6)	33(100.0)
Ceftriazone	15(45.5)	18(54.5)	33(100.0)
Ciprofloxacin	12(36.4)	21(63.6)	33(100.0)
Levofloxacin	18(54.5)	15(45.5)	33(100.0)
Amoxicillin	6(18.2)	27(81.8)	33(100.0)
Gentamycin	15(45.5)	18(54.5)	33(100.0)
Nalidixic acid	0(0.00)	33(100.0)	33(100.0)
Streptomycin	0(0.00)	33(100.0)	33(100.0)
Ampicillin	0(0.00)	33(100.0)	33(100.0)

The table shows that staphylococcus organisms showed sensitivity as compared to resistance to Levofloxacin (54.5%), Ceftriazone (45.5%), Ciprofloxacin (36.4%), and Augmentin (36.4%).

4. Discussion

The urinary tract which extends from the kidney to the urethral meatus and is usually sterile, has mechanisms that prevent infections, and the mechanisms include; acidity of urine, mucosal barriers, immunologic barriers and complete emptying of the urinary bladder during micturition¹². Some factors like pregnancy, diabetes and bladder outlet obstruction may cause immunologic, hormonal and mechanical changes that predispose to stasis and or urinary reflux resulting in the presence of bacteria in urine.^{13,14}

Routine culture techniques may yield growth of micro-organisms in some people who do not have symptoms of UTI, and expanded quantitative urine culture and sequencing techniques have identified bacterial growth in urine of healthy persons in whom routine urine culture did not yield growth of any organism; these urinary microbiomes are presumed to be responsible for sporadic UTI¹⁵. Accordingly, some experts have suggested using the term “urinary tract dysbiosis” in place of UTI because most pathologic bacteria are native to the urinary tract and their virulence may have been occasioned by a variation in the microbiota of the urinary tract¹⁶. The diagnosis of UTI which is based on Kass criterion propounded by Edward Kass in 1957 is premised on counting bacteria in fresh urine and urine bacteria count of one hundred thousand colony forming units or more is considered UTI¹⁷.

In this study 351 (76.97%) of the respondents were female while 105 (23.03%) were male. A study in Ogun state, Nigeria by Agu et al¹⁸ also had more female respondents compared to male. The age group with the highest frequency was 20-24 (table 1) and a similar age group had the highest frequency in the study by Agu et al¹⁸. This may be due to the fact that both studies were carried out in tertiary institutions and may indicate that most students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria fall within that age group.

A significant number, 165(36.29%) of those tested had bacterial growth. This is similar to what was found by other researchers^{18,19}. Recent and better methods of culturing bacteria in urine have shown that most people have bacteria in their urine and in fact even a wider spectrum^{18,19,20}. In a study by Anderson et al²¹ it was discovered that there were uncultured bacteria in women without symptoms of UTI. Similarly, Wolfe et al²² used high-throughput sequencing techniques to identify bacteria in patients without UTI. These may indicate that the number of people with no bacterial growth in our study may be lower if subjected to further testing. However, these advanced urine tests to identify bacteria are not routinely done because the IDSA does not recommend them⁹ and only pregnant women and those with significant risk of infection are treated for asymptomatic bacteriuria.⁸ However, as evidence shows that the micro-

organisms that cause UTI may have been in the urine long before the onset of symptoms^{15,16,19}, a good knowledge of the type of bacteria present in urine is necessary and will help guide empirical treatment of UTI.

The age group with the highest number of people with bacteria growth in their urine was 25-29 years. This was statistically significant with a p value of 0.015 (table 2). Odoki et al²³ in their study found that the prevalence of UTI was highest in the age group 20-29. This was similar to what we found in our study. The prevalence of UTI increases with age²⁴ but the study population were students of a university where most students are young. Aging is associated with hormonal and mechanical changes that may predispose to UTI, however in the young, the peak of uncomplicated UTI correlates with maximum sexual activity between the ages of 18 and 39 years.²⁵ This may mean that those between the ages of 25-29 in this study have the maximum sexual activity because this study was carried out among sexually active students.

The distribution of the most bacteria cultured as shown in table 3 were E coli 105(63.6%), S. aureus and Klebsiella spp. Schmiemann et al²⁶ also reported that E. coli caused most of the cases of complicated and uncomplicated UTI. In a study among pregnant women in Pakistan by Tabinda et al²⁷ the most common cause of asymptomatic bacteriuria was also E. coli followed by Klebsiella and Staphylococcus spp. These are similar to what was found in our study. Other studies by Agu et al¹⁸, and Bhayani et al²⁸ also found E. coli to be the most common cause of asymptomatic bacteriuria.

The sensitivity pattern showed that E. coli was most sensitive to Levofloxacin, ciprofloxacin and gentamycin as shown in table 4. This was similar to studies by Agu et al¹⁸. Oluwole et al²⁹ reported fluoroquinolones had the highest sensitivity patterns to E. coli. Klebsiella and S. aureus were also sensitive to Levofloxacin and ciprofloxacin (tables 5 and 6). These medications may be used for empiric treatment of UTI while waiting for the results of urine culture.

5. Conclusion

The knowledge of the types of micro-organisms that cause asymptomatic bacteriuria is important because similar organisms cause symptomatic UTI. The sensitivity of these organisms to antibiotics helps guide presumptive use of antibiotics in treatment of UTI. The most common organism implicated in asymptomatic bacteriuria is E. coli. The commonly culture organisms were most sensitive to levofloxacin and ciprofloxacin.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank the students' representatives of the various courses and departments who assisted us during sample collection. We also thank the entire staff of FUTU Health Centre for their assistance, especially Esther Ibe, Ijeoma Orji and Chukwuma Kinsley the Medical Laboratory Scientists who assisted in processing the samples.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

Approval for this study was received from the ethical committee of the institution.

Statement of informed consent

All patients recruited for the study gave written consent before their data and samples were collected. Results of the urine culture were not disclosed to any other person.

References

- [1] Foxman, B. The epidemiology of urinary tract infection. *Nat Rev Urol.* 2010, 7:653–660. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrurol.2010.190>
- [2] Odoki M, et al. Prevalence of Bacterial Urinary Tract Infections and Associated Factors Among Patients Attending Hospitals in Bushenyi District, Uganda. *Int J Microbiol.* 2019, 2019:4246780. PubMed PMID: 30906323.

- [3] Jombo, G.T., Egah, Do, Z., Banwat, E. B. and Ayeni, J. A. Nosocomial and Community Acquired Urinary tract infections at a teaching hospital in North Central Nigeria: findings from a study of 121,458 urine samples” Nigerian Journal of Medicine 2006, 15(3): 230 – 36, Available at: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/njon/article/view/37115>
- [4] Akinsete AM, Ezeaka C. Prevalence and risk factors of asymptomatic bacteriuria among children living with HIV in Lagos, Nigeria. Pan African Medical Journal. 2018 Nov 14, 31(1).
- [5] Little P, Merriman R, Turner S, Rumsby K, Warner G, Lowes JA, Smith H, Hawke C, Leydon G, Mullee M, Moore MV. Presentation, pattern, and natural course of severe symptoms, and role of antibiotics and antibiotic resistance among patients presenting with suspected uncomplicated urinary tract infection in primary care: observational study. *Bmj*. 2010 Feb 5, 340.
- [6] Delzell JE, and Lefevre ML. Urinary tract infections during pregnancy. *Am Fam Physician* 2000, 61: 713-21.
- [7] Olamijulo JA, Adewale CO, Olaleye O. Asymptomatic bacteriuria among antenatal women in Lagos. *J Obstet Gynaecol*. 2016, 36(6):722-725. doi:10.3109/01443615.2016.1148675
- [8] Karikari AB, Saba CKS, Yamik DY. Assessment of asymptomatic bacteriuria and sterile pyuria among antenatal attendants in hospitals in northern Ghana. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2020, 20(1):239. Published 2020 Apr 22. doi:10.1186/s12884-020-02936-6
- [9] Shaikh N, Osio VA, Wessel CB, Jeong JH. Prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria in children: a meta-analysis. *The Journal of Pediatrics*. 2020 Feb 1, 217:110-7.
- [10] Sonkar N, Banerjee M, Gupta S, Ahmad A. Asymptomatic bacteriuria among pregnant women attending tertiary care hospital in Lucknow, India. *Dubai Medical Journal*. 2021, 4(1):18-25.
- [11] US Preventive Services Task Force. Screening for asymptomatic bacteriuria. In: *Guide to clinical preventive services*. 2nd edition. 1996. Available at: <http://www.ahcpr.gov/clinic/uspstfix.htm>.
- [12] Nguyen HT. Bacterial infections of the genitourinary tract. In Tanagho EA, McAninch JW Editors: *Smith’s General Urology* 17th edition, Mc GrawHill USA
- [13] Amala SE, Nwokah EG. Prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria among pregnant women attending antenatal in Port Harcourt Township, Nigeria and antibiogram of isolated bacteria. *Am J Biomed Sci*. 2015, 7(2):125-33.
- [14] Worku GY, Alamneh YB, Abegaz WE. Prevalence of bacterial urinary tract infection and antimicrobial susceptibility patterns among diabetes mellitus patients attending Zewditu memorial hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Infection and Drug Resistance*. 2021, 14:1441.
- [15] Groah SL, Pérez-Losada M, Caldovic L, Ljungberg IH, Sprague BM, Castro-Nallar E, et al. Redefining Healthy Urine: A Cross-Sectional Exploratory Metagenomic Study of People with and without Bladder Dysfunction. *J Urol*. 2016, 196(2): 579-87 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.juro.2016.01.088>.
- [16] Morand A, Cornu F, Dufour JC, Tsimaratos M, Lagier JC, Raoult D. Human Bacterial Repertoire of the Urinary Tract: A Potential Paradigm Shift. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2019, 57(3): 675-18.
- [17] Kass EH. Bacteriuria and the diagnosis of infections of the urinary tract, with observations on the use of methionine as a urinary antiseptic. *AMA Arch Intern Med* 1957, 100:709–714. doi: 10.1001/archinte.1957.00260110025004. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- [18] Agu GC, Shoyemi WR, Out UJ, Afolabi BT Prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria in healthy tertiary institution students in Ijebu-north of Ogun state, Nigeria. *FUW Trends in Science & Technology Journal* 2020: 5, 348 – 353
- [19] Amala SE, Karibi-Botoye R, Nwokah EG, Pius MT. Prevalence of Asymptomatic Bacteriuria in Pregnancy and Urinary Tract Infection in Non-pregnant Symptomatic Womem. *American Journal of Biomedical Sciences* 2021, 13(4): 172-183
- [20] Khasriya R, Sathiananthamoorthy S, Ismail S, Kelsey M, Wilson M, Rohn JL, Malone-Lee J. Spectrum of bacterial colonization associated with urothelial cells from patients with chronic lower urinary tract symptoms. *J Clin Microbiol* 2013, 51: 2054–2062. doi: 10.1128/JCM.03314-12. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- [21] Anderson M, Bollinger D, Hagler A, Hartwell H, Rivers B, Ward K, Steck TR. Viable but nonculturable bacteria are present in mouse and human urine specimens. *J Clin Microbiol* 2004, 42:753–758. doi: 10.1128/JCM.42.2.753-758.2004. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]

- [22] Wolfe AJ, Toh E, Shibata N, Rong R, Kenton K, FitzGerald M et al. Evidence of uncultivated bacteria in the adult female bladder. *J Clin Microbiol* 2012, 50: 1376–1383. doi: 10.1128/JCM.05852-11. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
- [23] Odoki M, et al. Prevalence of Bacterial Urinary Tract Infections and Associated Factors Among Patients Attending Hospitals in Bushenyi District, Uganda. *Int J Microbiol*. 2019, 2019:4246780. PubMed PMID: 30906323.
- [24] Schmiemann G, Kniehl E, Gebhardt K, et al. The diagnosis of urinary tract infection: a systematic review. *Dtsch Arztebl Int* 2010, 107: 361–367
- [25] Alos JI. Epidemiology and etiology of urinary tract infection in the community. Antimicrobial susceptibility of the main pathogens and clinical significance of resistance. *Enfermedades Infecciosas y Microbiología Clínica* 2005; 23: 3-8
- [26] Schmiemann G, Kniehl E, Gebhardt K, et al. The diagnosis of urinary tract infection: a systematic review. *Dtsch Arztebl Int* 2010; 107: 361–367
- [27] Qazi T, Ainuddin J. Prevalence and Causative Organisms of Asymptomatic Bacteriuria among Pregnant Women in Karachi, Pakistan. *Journal of the College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka* 2021, 27: 360-367
- [28] Bhayani P, Rawekar R, Bawankule S, Kumar S, Acharya S, Gaidhane A et al. Profile of urinary tract infection in a rural tertiary care hospital: Two-year cross-sectional study. *Journal of Datta Meghe Institute of Medical Sciences University* 2019, 14(1): 22.
- [29] Oluwole OM, Emmanuel AD, Isaiah DA. Occurrence and Antibiotic Susceptibility Profiles of Biofilm-Forming Bacteria Associated with Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Among Students. *Res. J. Microbiol* 2022, 17 (1): 36-43